

PROSPECTS OF CREATING "KUPKARI" FOOTWEAR FOR EQUESTRIAN SPORT

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The first world equestrian games were held for the first time in 1990 in stockholm in order to unite in one place and at this time six equestrian disciplines: training, show jumping, triathlon, driving, endurance and aerobatics. Since 2010, eight equestrian disciplines have been represented: show jumping, dressage, complex, endurance, driving, aerobatics, reining and para-competitive dressage.

The Presidential Resolution № PP-5211 of 05. 08. 2021 "On State Program of development of horse breeding, equestrian sport, modern pentathlon and polo in Uzbekistan till 2025" says that Uzcharmsanoat association, association of craftsmen will attract foreign investors in 2021 to take measures to localize production of necessary sportswear, equipment and instruments for equestrian sport.

Kupkari is one of the ancient mass, national games of the peoples of central asia. It was mainly held on the occasion of victory and harvest festivals, weddings and folk festivals. The game "kupkari" is organized in different places according to different rules (called chartak, drag, finish, race, packka, minbar and other names). The purpose of this game to educate boys and young men to be brave, agile and courageous, and not just for fun.

Kupkari games helped improve horse breeding and increase the number of hardy, impetuous breeds. Karabair, arabian, akhalteke, kurama, lakai, kustanai, karabakh and eagle horses are among the kupkari. Kupkari (ulak, buzkashi) is a traditional equestrian competition among the peoples of central asia. (in translation from turkic "kup" means "many" and persian "kari" means "deed, work", i. e. "deed of many"). The race consists of 2 rounds: the rider race (horse race) and the ulak race. In order for the ulak to hit the designated place in the race from the goat, the rider must saddle the horse, lift the goat from the ground and bring it to the finish line. In recent years, kupkari games have entered the sport, and uzbekistan began to hold official competitions and international tournaments across the country.

Equestrian athletes need special footwear. The right footwear not only protects the sock, but also makes it easier for riders to work during training. There are many

kinds of shoes for riders, and their models and colors vary. The choice of shoes will depend on what kind of equestrian sport is used for. In addition, equestrian shoes require special care. The most appropriate footwear for the cupcari games is boots. Riding boots are quite narrow-nosed, have a thin and smooth sole and a high heel (up to 5 cm); they have high cuffs ending below the knee and tightly fitting calves. It does not restrict movement and supports the arch of the foot.

The highest quality boots are made of leather, but there are cheaper - leatherette, rubber and even plastic. To determine the size, you need to know the following parameters: length of foot (insole length), shin girth at its widest part, height of boots - the length of the notch under the kneecap to the bottom point of the heel. For the length of the foot it is better to take boots with half a size reserve.

For the game "kupkari" boots are designed on the basis of a model of the upper of men's boots made of chrome-tanned leather with a sleeve neck of the front. developed a set of requirements of special shoes for the game "kupkari" on the basis of a questionnaire survey. Participants in the game prefers boots with high cuffs, high heel classical style. shape of the cuff asymmetrical. materials of leather uppers.

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